

Supplementary Information #3: estimating the foetal age of modern individuals

Skeletal measurements should be strongly linked to foetal age, yet this variable is hardly ever known, even for modern individuals. Indeed, the exact foetal age depends on two events, conception date and birth, that are, especially for the former, not always known. Exploring links between foetal size and age are thus not straightforward.

Available data on rut and calving periods are summarised in Supplementary Information #4. In Finland, Norway (Svalbard excluded) and Sweden, rut periods reported by different authors span from the 25th of September to the 19th of October, and calving periods from the 5th of May to the 7th of June, with a peak around mid-May (SI #4). For reindeer, implantation is not delayed (Leader-Williams & Rosser, 1983), and Roine *et al.* (1982) considered that the majority of hinds had conceived by the 10th of October. Estimates of the gestation period vary between 209 and 240 days (Leader-Williams & Rosser, 1983), while a mean gestation period of 221 days (211 to 229) was reported for reindeer populations at the Kutuharju Field Reindeer Research Station, in Kaamanen, Finland (Mysterud *et al.*, 2009), similar to the estimate of 220 days by Roine *et al.* (1982).

Thus, despite an important variability, we used in our study mean values for conception and birth around, respectively, the 10th of October and the 18th of May, with a mean of 221 days of gestation.

In our sample, the exact development age of each individual at death is only known for 7 individuals (Table 1). A finding date was recorded in the Oulu Museum database, but the exact time span between death and foetus discovery is, in most cases, unknown (however, given that they are very attractive to predators, who would have destroyed or at least damaged the bones, it is likely that they died shortly before being found). Rather than using this small sample ($n = 7$), we estimated foetal age (in weeks) using data provided by Roine *et al.* (1982), who studied a much larger sample also from Finland. Using their data (Roine *et al.*, 1982: their Table 1), the following 2-degree polynomial regression equation between mean metacarpal length (MC1) and foetal age (in weeks) was obtained: $y = -0.0015x^2 + 0.3691x + 7.808$ ($R^2 = 0.9961$). MC1 measurements from our sample were then used to estimate foetal age (in weeks). For 11 individuals, MC1 could not be measured: F2 was thus used to estimate MC1 (F2 and MC1 are highly correlated, $r = 0.92$; $p < 0.001$), and subsequently the estimated age. The comparison of estimated age with the known age of 7 individuals shows good agreement, with a mean difference of 2.44 weeks, and a maximum of 5.64 weeks (Table 1). These differences could be due to a different date of conception (here, all ages using the death date assume a conception on the 10th of October) or issues with the estimated age using skeletal measurements.

Figure 1 compares finding date, estimated age and several independent measurements of foetal size (weight and body length as recorded in the Zoological Museum of the University of Oulu database, MC1

and F2 skeletal measurements). Estimated age and finding date are correlated ($r = 0.88$), but estimated age is more strongly correlated with the different measures of foetal size (Figure 1). Hence, the estimated age computed in this study appears to be a better estimation of foetal age compared to the finding date.

Individual	Death information	Finding date	MeanAge¹ (weeks)	EstimAge² (weeks)	Difference (1 - 2)
18861	in the uterus from bear-killed mother	31/05/1979	33.43	27.79	+5.64
18862	in the uterus from wolverine-killed mother	24/04/1979	28.14	28.93	-0.79
18863	in the uterus from wolverine-killed mother	28/04/1979	28.71	29.09	-0.37
18865	1 day old, killed by bear	31/05/1979	33.43	29.06	+4.36
18868	0 day old, died in labour	28/05/1982	33.00	30.30	+2.70
24273	4 days old	24/05/1989	32.43	30.40	+2.03
24766	about 1 day old	15/05/1990	31.14	29.94	+1.20

Table 1: Summary of information provided by the Oulu Museum on the death of seven individuals. 1: the “MeanAge” column corresponds to the number of weeks between a mean date of conception (10th of October) and the date of death. 2: “EstimAge” is the estimated age (in weeks) computed using skeletal measurements (cf. text for more details).

Figure 1: Correlations between estimated age (weeks, cf. main text), finding date (expressed as number of days since the 1st of January), foetal weight (g), body length (mm), metacarpal and humerus lengths (mm). Diagonal: histogram of measurements. Lower triangle: bivariate scatterplots of measurements. Upper triangle: Pearson correlation statistic (*: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$).

References

Leader-Williams, N., Rosser, A.M. 1983. Ovarian characteristics and reproductive performance of reindeer, *Rangifer tarandus*. - *Journal of Reproduction and Fertility* 67: 247–256.

<https://doi.org/10.1530/jrf.0.0670247>

Mysterud, A., Røed, K.H., Holand, Ø., Yoccoz, N.G., Nieminen, M. 2009. Age-related gestation length adjustment in a large iteroparous mammal at northern latitude. - *Journal of Animal Ecology* 78:

1002–1006. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2656.2009.01553.x>

Roine, K., Nieminen, M., Timisjärvi, J. 1982. Foetal Growth in the Reindeer. - *Acta vet. scand.* 23:

107–117. <https://doi.org/10.1186/BF03546827>